

Snakemake Multiextension Support for named In- & Output

1 Multiextension Support for In- & Output

1.1 Authors

- [Ward Deboutte](#) - Max Planck Institute of Immunobiology and Epigenetics, Freiburg, Germany
- [Johannes Köster](#) - University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany

1.2 Associated Project Workitem

This hackathon work item was based on [a user issue](#) and ultimately solved with this [pull request](#).

1.3 Problem

Previously, Snakemake's `multiext` function allowed defining multiple output files with different extensions for a single rule output. However, it did not support assigning *named* output files. This limitation hindered users who needed to generate multiple distinct output files from a single rule, each requiring a specific extension, and needed to refer to them by name in subsequent rules. Users were forced to use less clean workarounds. We had a feature request to solve this issue, and as it significantly improved the readability and maintainability of Snakemake workflows that require multiple outputs with different formats it was selected as a work item during the hackathon.

1.4 Solution

This work item introduces named output support for the `multiext` function, allowing users to specify both the extension and a name for each output file. The core changes involved modifying the `multiext` definitions in the `io` module and associated code in the `path_modifier` and `rules` modules to correctly handle the named extensions and make them accessible within the rule context.

1.4.1 Code Example

The following Snakemake rule demonstrates the use of named outputs with the `multiext` function.

```
rule named:
  input:
    'dat.txt'
  output:
    multiext("columns", out1 = ".foo", out2 = ".bar"),
  shell: '''
    cut -f1 {input} > {output.out1}
    cut -f2 {input} > {output.out2}
```